

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization

COLD TOLERANCE

Spikelet sterility in winter rice

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Spikelet sterility appeared at epidemic levels in farmers' fields of the North Telangana Zone of Andhra Pradesh in winter 1983-84. Average minimum temperatures 20 d before flowering, from 26 Feb to 4 Mar 1984, were around 15 °C (range 13.7-16.8 °C). In 1983, temperatures averaged 21.3 °C during the corresponding period.

We screened 22 rice varieties sown in the 1983-84 winter season for spikelet sterility. Entries were planted in 10-m² plots at 10- × 15-cm spacing in a randomized block design with 4 replications.

Sterile and healthy spikelets on 10 randomly selected panicles in each plot were counted. Genotypic differences for spikelet sterility were significant.

Sterility and grain yield of 22 rice cultivars under low temperature, 26 Feb-4 Mar 1984.

Variety	Sterility (%)	Grain yield (t/ha)
NLR26706	2.7	5.8
MTU 2400	5.6	5.8
WGL 47877	6.4	5.7
RNR29692	6.5	5.9
WGL 26358	6.7	5.5
WGL 48828	7.1	5.8
WGL 48684	7.4	5.3
WGL 33808	7.7	5.4
Pothana	8.5	5.9
Tella Hamsa	8.7	5.0
WGL 48001	8.8	5.1
WGL 6861	9.3	5.4
MTU6286	9.9	5.1
C73905	10.0	5.8
MTU6910	10.3	4.6
WGL 39966	10.4	5.7
IR50	12.3	6.0
RNR99181	12.8	5.9
WGL 44645	13.2	5.8
RNR99377	14.6	5.8
IR13525	17.0	5.4
WGL 33343	18.1	5.0

Sterility varied from 2.7 to 18%. The lowest was in NLR26706 and the highest in WGL 33343 (see table).

Varieties NLR26706, MTU2400,

RNR29692, and WGL 26358 recorded higher grain yields with low sterility and can be used in low temperature zones and in breeding programs. □

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization

DROUGHT TOLERANCE

Response of short-duration rice cultivars to drought stress

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Twenty early-maturing rice cultivars from different sources were evaluated during the 1985 and 1986 wet seasons (WS) (Jun-Oct) under upland rainfed conditions along with check DR92 (a released variety) in a randomized block design with three replications. Seeds were sown directly in 6.0-m² plots with a

spacing of 20 cm between rows and 10 cm within rows. Soil preparation, fertilization (60-60-40 kg NPK/ ha), and weeding were as in standard, well-managed plot trials.

Rainfall was normal during 1985 WS but erratic in 1986, with a 16-d drought spell. The maturity period of all cultivars was longer by 2 to 27 d in 1986 because of severe drought stress (see table). The long drought spell and the prolonged maturity period reduced grain yield 10-91%. A significant and positive correlation ($r = 0.727$) was obtained between maturity prolongation and yield reduction due to drought stress.

Performance of rice cultivars under drought stress. Bhubaneswar, India, 1985-86.

Cultivar	Days to maturity		Yield (t/ha)		
	1985	1986	1985	1986	Yield reduction (%)
DR83-1	91	104	2.7	1.5	45
DR83-2	91	104	2.7	1.3	52
OR165-93-15	89	104	2.4	0.3	88
ORKM6	94	110	2.3	0.8	65
DR83-16	98	110	2.1	0.8	62
OR165-97-15	90	112	2.1	0.2	91
IET7613	89	100	2.1	0.5	76
IET7566	89	105	2.0	0.7	65
DR83-3	90	109	2.0	0.5	75
OR165-86-12	90	113	2.0	0.4	80
ORKM4	91	105	1.9	0.6	69
IET7564	92	119	1.7	0.2	88
IET7617	102	116	1.4	0.6	58
IET7261	102	114	1.3	0.8	37
IET7635	104	118	1.3	0.5	62
IET7625	105	120	1.2	0.8	34
IET7633	114	116	1.0	0.9	10
IET7614	102	112	0.7	0.7	-
IET7911	102	112	0.2	0.2	-
DR92 (check)	91	102	2.6	1.2	54
CD (0.05)			0.3	0.2	

The yield differences among the entries were significant in both years. DR cultivars recorded higher yields than IET or OR cultivars. DR83-1 and DR83-2 in both normal and drought years outyielded the other entries, indicating their drought tolerance capacity. □

Response of rainfed upland rice to chlormequat chloride

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Upland, rainfed rice yields in Orissa are very low because of continuous drought. The use of a growth retardant on rice may improve crop yield by enabling the plant to resist drought through root proliferation.

We studied the effect of chlormequat chloride on the grain yield of rice at the Regional Research Station, Semiliguda, in Jun-Sep 1979. The soil was a clay loam (Ochrept) with pH 5.5, 0.852% organic matter, 9.5 kg available P/ha, cation exchange capacity 8.5 meq/100 g soil, and water-holding capacity 45%. Parijat (100 d duration) and Subhadra (90 d) were the test varieties.

The crops suffered from intermittent drought at various growth stages

Table 1. Stages of growth and drought spells suffered by the crop. Semiliguda, Orissa, India, Jun-Sep 1979.

Plant age	Drought conditions
<i>Seedling</i>	
Germination to day 4	No drought
Day 5 to 19	Drought
<i>Vegetative</i>	
Day 20 to 40	No drought
Day 41 to 52	Drought
Day 53	No drought
<i>Reproductive</i>	
Day 54 to 60	Drought
Day 61 to 62	No drought
Day 63 to 68	Drought
Day 69	No drought
<i>Flowering and ripening</i>	
Day 70 until harvest	Drought

Table 2. Effect of chlormequat chloride on rice yield. Semiliguda, Orissa, India, Jun-Sep 1979.

Chlormequat chloride (ppm)	Sprays (no.)	Time of spray (d after germination)	Grain yield (t/ha)	
			Parijat	Subhadra
0 (water)	—	—	2.0	1.5
500	1	25	2.1	1.8
1000	1	25	2.2	1.8
500	2	25,40	2.4	1.9
1000	2	25,40	2.3	1.8
CD (0.05)	—	—	0.3	0.1

(Table 1). After germination, chlormequat chloride at 500 and 1,000 ppm was sprayed once or twice.

Both varieties yielded significantly

higher when 500 ppm chlormequat chloride was sprayed twice (Table 2). The response was higher in Subhadra than in Parijat. □

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization ADVERSE SOILS TOLERANCE

Screening for zinc deficiency tolerance in rice

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Zn deficiency is becoming a major nutritional problem limiting rice yield. Genetic variability for tolerating it exists in rice genotypes. During the 1985 wet season at Pusa, severe Zn deficiency was observed in a varietal trial of 16 entries

grown in 15-m² plots in 3 replications. The symptoms were severe 25-30 d after transplanting. The soil was a light, extremely calcareous (free CaCO₃ 39%) sandy loam (organic C 0.48%, pH 8.6, EC 0.50 dS/m).

Scoring was based on percentage of hills affected in a plot (see table). Zn content of the third leaf from the top (five leaves from each replication, bulked) was determined with an atomic absorption spectrophotometer. Tolerant varieties had higher Zn concentration in

Zinc tolerance in rice varieties. Bihar, India, 1985 wet season.

IET no.	Designation	Cross	Score ^a	Zn concentration (ppm)
3279	CR126-42-2	Dungansali/IR8	3	28
—	NC1626	Selection from land races	1	38
7614	RP1451-1712-4319	Rasi/Fine Gora	3	29
7613	RP1670-1418-2205-1582	M63-83/Cauvery	3	24
6148	TNAU6464	Bala/CO 13	3	28
7254	TNAU(AD)103	Tiruveni/Amravathi CO 3	3	27
7564	RP1667-301-1196-1562	IRAT8/N22	7	16
7616	RP1888-4259-1529-126	RP79-5/Tella Vadlu	5	22
—	IR25588-7-3-1	IR19657-37-3/IR9129-209-2-2	7	14
—	Pusa 4-11	Tadukan/IRB	7	16
—	Pusa 33	Improved Sabarmati/Ratna	7	19
—	Pusa 2-21	IR8/TKM6	7	17
—	ES29-5-3	—	9	13
—	RAU4004-127	—	9	12
6223	CR222-MW10	MTU15/Waikoku	9	13
—	IR25890-82-5-3	RP825-714-II/CR113-32// IR9129-209-2-2	9	13

^aBased on percentage of hills affected in a plot: 1 < 1%, 3 = 1-5%, 5 = 6-25%, 7 = 26-50%, 9 = 51-100%.